

The Military Expedition of the Mughals in Northeast India: Some Aspects

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Introduction

The main objective of this paper is to highlight the impact of the military expedition of the Mughal rulers in northeast India. The main places of contests were Darrang, Kampur, Hajo, Saraighat, Guwahati etc. All these places are as famous in Persian version of the conflicts as in the Assamese chronicles. The military expedition of the Mughals in northeast India paved the way of consolidation and extension of the Mughal dominion towards the north-eastern parts by which the Mughals not only extended their territory, but also controlled the administration of this area. As a matter of fact, the military expeditions of the Mughals in northeast India and their impact on the society and culture form one of the most interesting, but little known subject of the region. It offers an almost unexplored and uninvestigated field of study. Though some writers have dealt with it in their own way, but so far no detailed work has been carried out. This research paper is largely based on *Baharistan-i-Ghaibi*, *Assam Buranji*, *Tripura Buranji*, *Ain-i-Akbari*, *Sri Rajmala* and other contemporary literature and brings Tripura in focus.

Survey of Literature

The *Akbar Nama* of Shaikh Abul Fazl throws ample light on the beginnings of an aggressive in the eastern India. In this book the military expedition of the Mughals finds lots of significance such as- the establishment of a defensive alliance with Koch Behar, the break-up of the Koch kingdom, the events of the Koch-Mughal war especially the imprisonment of Raja Parikshit and Mukarram Khan's expedition to Assam.¹ *Ain-i-Akbari* also mentions the fatigue and dangers of various military expeditions coupled with the climatic conditions and environmental tensions of the pestilential country. Abul Fazl describes the extent of the Koch Kingdom and its products especially in horses and elephants and the intervention of Isa Khan and Man Singh in the Koch affairs and the expedition of Kalapahar and Mukarram Khan to Assam. He also mentions that the Koch Army at that time consisted of 4000 horses, 20,000 infantry, 700

elephant and 1000 war boats. The amazing accounts of magic, sorcery and witch-craft was so impressive that even the medieval doyen like Abul Fazl while talking of the prosperous silk industry of the region, never forgets to mention that the people of Kamrupa are very good looking and addicted to the practice of magic.² Abdul Qadir Badauni, the author of *Muntakhab-ut-Tawarikh* has described the city of Lakhnauti and elaborated the political relations of Bengal Sultans with the Mughals with some light on contact between Assam and the Mughals. The main Mughal sources for the history of Bengal and Assam contemporary to the reign of Jahangir is *Tuzuk-i-Jahangiri*, which is an autobiography of Emperor Jahangir. This book provides the information related to hostility between Lakshmi Narayan, king of Koch Behar and Parikshit Narayan, king of Kamrup, which was the main reason of Ahom-Mughal conflict during the last quarter of 16th century.

The author of the *Baharistan-i-Ghaybi* is Ala al-Din Isfahani alias Mirza Nathan, a contemporary military officer in Mughal Kamrupa, who took a leading part in all the campaigns in Bengal and Assam during the reign of Jahangir and also in the rebellion of Shahjahan during his occupation of Bengal. The *Baharistan-i-Ghaybi* is practically the only contemporary and authentic account for the period with which it deals. The chief value of the work lies in it as it supplies information about the wars of the Mughals with the Ahoms, Koches, Kacharis, the Afghans of Sylhet, the hill tribes of Assam and the Rajas of Tippera and Aracan.

The book *Faithiyah-i-Ibriyah* by Shihabal Din Talish is the most authentic account of Assam written in Persian and it narrates the description of Mir Jumla's invasion of Assam. It also incorporates an account of Koch-Mughal affairs during Shaista Khan's Vice Royalty in Bengal along with descriptive account of the social and political condition of Assam of those days. As Talis accompanied Mir Jumla in his military campaigns in Koch Behar and Assam, his account is like an eye-witness account. It describes the various aspects of military and revenue administration of the land. This book also narrates in detail about all the events that occurred at the time of Mir Jumla's invasion of Assam in 1662-1663 A.D.

The book *Padshah Nama* written by Abdul Hamid Lahori, the official historian of Mughal Emperor Shah Jahan describes domestic conflict between Lakshmi Narayan of Koch Bihar and Parikshit. Narayan of Koch Hajo, the imprisonment of Parikshit

by the Mughals and their mutual hostility. Really, this is an authentic source book to trace the military expedition of the Mughals in northeast India.

Assamese Chronicles written in Assamese language, better known as *Buranjis* also throw ample light on the military campaigns of the Mughals. The three *Buranjis* named as the *Ahom Buranji* from Khunlung to Khunlai, the *Ahom Buranji* and the *Purani Asam Buranji* are equally important to know in detail about Ahom-Mughal conflicts.

E. A. Gait made certain references on the relation of the kingdom of Koch Behar and Kamrup with the Muslims in his work *The Koch Kings of Kamrupa* as well in his book *A History of Assam*, which has described the military campaigns of the Ahoms and the Mughals. In the modern period the book by J. N. Sarkar has also illustrated in detail about the Muslim campaigns in Assam in his famous book *Freedom Struggle in Medieval Assam. A Comprehensive History of Assam Vol. II* edited by H. K. Barpujari narrates elaborately about the military expedition of the Mughals in North-East India. He has also mentioned all the important events leading to Ahom-Mughal conflicts.

The Province of Tippera, which from time immemorial had been an independent kingdom, became annexed to the Mughal empire.³ But our view of the matter is that this did not mean the loss of independent status so far as the Hill Territory of Tripura is concerned. It was only the portion to the west and south of the present district of British Tippera that was converted into the Zamindari of Roshanabad. This fact can be made more clear if we look it, *An Atlas of the Mughal Empire : Political and Economic Maps with Detailed Notes, Bibliography and Index* (Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 1982) authored by Irfan Habib in Map No-II A, "He mentions Tripura as Tipara." *Ain-i-Akbari* does not assert Mughal suzerainty over but in *Iqbalnama* 'Tripura' is given as one of the three Mahals of Bengal that did not belong to any of its Sircars. A successful expedition against Tipara is described in *Baharistan-i-Ghaibi* (spells Tippera). The limits of the principality during 17th century were probably identical with those shown in Rennell's maps (spells Tiperah). It included the entire territory of Tripura (The older Tippera Hill tracts) and parts of the modern districts of Tippera. *Baharistan-i-Ghaibi* further informs Udaipur as the capital of Tippera, which signifies the integrity of Tripura.

As per *Ain-i-Akbari*, "The next worthy king after Deva Manikya was Vijay Manikya, who was a contemporary of Akbar. He was an independent King of Tripura."⁴ It is note-worthy to be mentioned that all the above-mentioned sources throw some light on the Ahom-Mughal conflicts, but none of these provided complete facts on the military expedition of the Mughals in North-East India as a whole as well as the impacts of the military expedition of the Mughals in North-East India find less importance.

In the present research paper attempts have been made to focus on the significant contributions of the Mughals to the distant societies of northeast India during the period of Ahom and Koch rulers. The present work aims at analyzing the impacts of the Mughal's invasion, which was felt in the political life of the Ahom and Koch kingdoms whereby owing to their repeated inroads they were able to introduce their own system of administration and political organizations which remained as legacies in the administrative set up of the region. It was due to the far reaching impacts of the military expedition of the Mughals in northeast India that was felt in the forms of economic impacts because of large scale trade and commerce in this period. Even religious and cultural impacts can be traced due to military expedition of the Mughals in North-East India. On the basis of above- mentioned facts, it is obvious that though the Mughals had prepared themselves in a better manner for the military expedition in North-East India, but they could not completely consolidated the vast empire in their first attempt, but many wars had to be fought to attain suzerainty over North-East India. It is true that the main political impact of the military expedition of the Mughals was to annex the vast territory in their power from Koch, Ahom and Manikya kings. After their victory they tried to administer the North-Eastern states as per their will and wish.

Impacts of the Expeditions

As a matter of fact, the military expedition of the Mughals witnessed a lot of impacts in North-East India. The people of North-East India not only faced the impacts boldly, but also provided immense help to the state. Some of the impacts can be summed up as follows:-

Cultural Impact

Culture plays an important role in moulding destiny of one's own country. The military expedition of the Mughals in North-East India was very much pivotal for the cultural impact. Two different religion, Hindu and Islam in addition to Buddhist tradition laid the formula of cultural synthesis in North-East India. Now, the North-East India witnessed the emergence of secular identity as the people of different religions just like Hindu, Muslim and Buddhists walked together to form a common cultural identity.

Muslims contribution in the field of historical writings in India is considered to be a remarkable cultural gift. Impact of Persian on Assamese language and literature has been the area of research till this day. A few works in this subject exist today but no study on the proposed theme has been undertaken till date. Therefore it is necessary to work on the proposed topic. This work shall focus on the study of Persian sources for the study of the history of medieval Assam and shall through sidelight on the geographical location and the Socio-Cultural and economic life of the then Assamese people.

Economic Impact

After studying all the historical side of the Mughal Inroads in North-East India, we can say that the Mughals led vast military expedition in North-East India to gain more from trade and commerce. They also wanted to get hold of the wild elephants for their warfare. They even wanted to get forest items & silk after their victory. The land revenue was also major economic factor. During the reign of Yasodhar Manikya Tripura was under the occupation of the Mughals for about three years (1618C.E.-1620C.E.). The invaders captured elephants and royal treasures. The Mughal army marauded and looted the wealth of the subjects.⁵ Thus, the wealth of Tripura flowed to the Mughal side and this small state faced a lot of economic problems.

During the reign of Kalyan Manikya (1628 C.E.-1660 C.E.) Tripura was invaded by the Bengal Subadar Shah Shuja, but no significant success was achieved even after labouring for one year. The district of Mirzafur was made the frontier of the Imperial dominion.⁶

It is interesting to note that in the revenue records of Bengal Suba revised at the time of Shah Shuja in 1658 C.E., Sarkar Udaipur was recorded as a revenue paying centre.⁷ The mention of Sarkar

Udaipur in all his land-grants is indicative of the Mughal allegiance, real or nominal, particularly for the western plains and thus beading Tripura full of Economic problems.

Religious Impact

Religious syncretism has occurred wherever different religions have met. In this regard it is stated that a natural Indian openness to new religious ideas convinced many immigrant Muslims that a life of peaceful coexistence should be the preferred option. The fact that Indian Sunnis have tolerated the presence of their Shia minority better than anywhere else in the Islamic world, and also allowed Sufi missionaries freedom to proselytize everywhere, are clear indications that Indians may have indeed taught immigrant Muslims the advantages of religious tolerance.

The Mughal inroads in North-East India led so many religious impacts. As we know that the Mughals followed 'Islam' religion, which is against of idol – worship. This is why, When Emperor Jehangir was in power of Delhi; at that time Bengal was in the command of Ibrahim Khan Fatejang and Mirza Nurulla Khan. Both these Governors of Bengal attacked Tripura and arrested its ruler Yasodhar Manikya and they prohibited the worship of Chaudda Devata and the Tripureswari Kali. They built a mosque at Udaipur and encouraged the Mullas, Pirs and Fakirs to convert some Hindus to Islam.⁸

Social Impact

A Man lives in the society. Social life forms the best platform of communal harmony. Before the inroads of Mughals, the North-East India formed peaceful co-existence of its people. But after the Mughal inroads, the people of North-East India knew the fact that self-help is the best help. So, they endeavoured to accept the latest means of a developed society. The people of this area had the feelings of sovereignty to retaliate the Mughal invaders. Many of them joined the military organization. Thus, it created a social mobilization among the people of North-East India.

Military Preparedness

After the Mughal expedition in North-East India, the military preparedness started in a better manner. The preparation of the army presupposed various factors like the development of the means of warfare, human, animal and material sources. It was

the demand of elephants for the preparation of war as well as to make boats from the forest wood emphasized the need of military campaigns of the Mughals. The Ahoms and Kochs found themselves totally prepared for the war strategies.

In an effort to modernize the army, Vijay Manikya (C.1532-1563 C.E.) of Tripura started organizing the Cavalry. He not only imported the horses, but also employed the Afghan soldiers⁹ in the branch and thus introduced a new element in the Tripura army, although according to *Ain-i-Akbari*, the strength of Tripura Cavalry was negligible.¹⁰

Impact on art and architecture

The Mughals had far reaching impact in the field of art & architecture in North-East India. Actually, it was the blend of Indo-Islamic style. For example:- In the construction of mosques & palaces of the kings the same style of art & architecture can be observed.

Conclusion

Thus, on the basis of above facts, we can say that the military expedition of the Mughals in North-East India was not transient in nature, but it was the outcome of constant endeavours from the Mughal Governors & their contingents. Though, they became successful in their endeavours, but they could not annex the states of Northeast India so easily and completely into the Mughal dominion. The annexation of Koch-Bihar by the Mughals ultimately inspired them to annex Kamrup. The early decades of the 17th century had far reaching effects in terms of the military expedition of the Mughals. The Ahom- Mughal conflicts refer to the period between the first Mughal attack on the Ahom kingdom in 1615 A.D. It may be mentioned that in the war against the Mughals, many of the neighbouring hill people sent their contingents and successfully fought against the invaders. In 1681 A.D., there ensued a period of weak and unstable government during which several weak and young kings were placed on the Ahom throne. By taking advantage of the situation, Laluk Barphukan, the Viceroy of Lower Assam at Gauhati treacherously handed Gauhati over to the Mughals.

Except a small portion of its territory, remaining part of Tripura never fell prey to the Mughals. The historical documents like *Akbar Nama*, *Tuzuk-i-Jahangiri*, *Ain-i-Akbari*, *Baharistan-i-Ghaibi*, *Tripura Buranjis*, *Sri Rajmala* & many significant source materials provide the authenticity of the military expedition of the

Mughals in Northeast India. If we critically analyze the Mughal campaigns in Northeast India, we find that their economic impact, religious impact, cultural impact, social impact as well as impact on military preparedness formed pivotal role in making Northeast India as a modern one. Of course, the military expedition of the Mughals in Northeast India proved to be a lesson of motivation, patriotic feelings, self-awareness and a challenging task for the people of Northeast India.

Notes and References

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